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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ORAL IN SITU GEL CONTAINING REPAGLINDE

Shubhechha Bansod, Vaishnavi Bankar, Manisha S. Karpe, Vilasrao J. Kadam

University of Mumbai, Bharati Vidyapeeth's College of Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutics, C.B.D. Belapur, Sector 8, Navi Mumbai- 400614, India.

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ABSTRACT

Gel dosage forms are successfully used as drug delivery systems to control drug release and protect the medicaments from a hostile environment. The main objective is to formulate and evaluate in situ oral gels of repaglinide based on the concept of pH triggered and ion activated systems. The system utilizes polymers that exhibit sol-to-gel phase transition due to change in specific physico-chemical parameters. A pH triggered system consisting of Carbopol 934P (0.2-1.2% w/v) was used to prolong the release of repaglinide (0.1% w/v). Formulations were evaluated for gelling capacity, viscosity, gel strength, floating studies, spreadability, and in vitro release. The use of Carbopol as an in situ gel forming system was substantiated by the property to transform into stiff gels when the pH was raised. The drug content, clarity, and pH of the formulation were found to be satisfactory. The viscosity was found to be in the range 5 to 85 centipoise for the sol, whereas for the gels it was up to 16000 centipoise. The formulation showed pseudo plastic flow with thixotropy. The maximum gel strength (using texture analyser). The optimized formulations were able to release the drug up to 6 h. As it is a floating drug delivery system it shows increased retention and increased bioavailability of drugs.

Corresponding author

Shubhechha Bansod

Bharati Vidyapeeth's College of Pharmacy,
Department of Pharmaceutics,
C.B.D. Belapur, Sector 8,
Navi Mumbai.
bansodshubhechha@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Floating drug delivery system is one of the important approaches to achieve gastric retention to obtain sufficient drug bioavailability. This delivery systems is desirable for drugs with an absorption window in the stomach or in the upper small intestine. This have a bulk density less then gastric fluids and so remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period and the drug is released slowly as a desired rate from the system. After release of drug, the residual system is emptied from the stomach. This result in an increased gastric retention time (GRT) and a better control of the fluctuation in plasma drug concentration. The gel formed from in situ gelling system, being lighter than gastric fluids, floats over the stomach contents or adhere to gastric mucosa due to presence of bioadhesive nature of polymer and produce gastric retention of dosage form and increase gastric residence time resulting in prolonged drug delivery in gastrointestinal tract.

AIM AND RATIONALE

The present research is about gastro retentive drug delivery systems in the form of in-situ gels. Advanced research is carried out to develop novel drug delivery systems to alter the pharmacokinetics of the drugs. Drug release from the delivery devices are usually sustained at the target sites for many drugs using current release technologies. The main accent during the development of oral controlled release dosage forms is to prolong the residence time of the dosage form in the stomach or upper gastrointestinal (GI) tract until the drug is completely released. To achieve the retention of dosage unit in stomach many approaches have emerged like bioadhesive systems, swelling and expanding systems, floating systems, modified shape systems, high-density systems and other delayed gastric emptying devices. Gel dosage forms are successfully used as drug delivery systems to control drug release and protect the medicaments from a hostile environment. In situ gel formulation has received considerable attention over the past few years and increasing number of in situ gelling systems have been investigated and many patents for their use in various biomedical applications including drug delivery have been reported. In situ gels are the liquid formulations which undergo conversion in to semisolid form under influence of various stimuli like change in pH, temperature etc. While the system is floating on gastric contents, the drug is released slowly at a desired rate from the system. Repaglinide has been selected as a model drug because it exhibits required pharmacokinetic and physico-chemical properties for controlled release. Repaglinide is a unique antidiabetic. Repaglinide is an oral antihyperglycemic agent used for the treatment of non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM). It belongs to the meglitinide class of short-acting insulin secretagogues, which act by binding to β cells of the pancreas to stimulate insulin release. Repaglinide induces an early insulin response to meals decreasing postprandial blood glucose levels. It should only be taken with meals and meal-time doses should be skipped with any skipped meal. Approximately one month of therapy is required before a decrease in fasting blood glucose is seen. Meglitinides may have a neutral effect on weight or cause a slight increase in weight. The average weight gain caused by meglitinides appears to be lower than that caused by sulfonylureas and insulin and appears to occur only in those naïve to oral antidiabetic agents. Due to their mechanism of action, meglitinides may cause hypoglycemia although the risk is thought to be lower than that of sulfonylureas since their action is dependent on the presence of glucose. . Repaglinide is extensively metabolized in the liver and excreted in bile. Repaglinide metabolites do not possess appreciable hypoglycemic activity.

MATERIALS

Repaglinide, Carbopol, sodium carboxy methyl cellulose, sodium citrate, calcium chloride, deionised water.

METHODS

Preparation of in situ gelling systems:

- Aqueous solutions of varying concentration containing Carbopol 934P were prepared and evaluated for gelling capacity and viscosity in order to identify the composition suitable for as in situgelling systems (Formulation codes CF1, CF2, CF3 and CF4).
- Many experiments were conducted by varying the concentration of these polymer (carbopol) in order to identify the optimum concentration required for the gel forming solution.
- Dispersion containing Carbopol 934P of different concentration (0.2-1.2% w/v) were initially prepared in pH 7 phosphate buffer solutions.
- Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose was added in deionised water containing sodium citrate and was heated to 90 degrees Celsius.
- This was further cooled to 40 degrees Celsius and calcium chloride was added.
- In another container the drug was dissolved in organic solvent and both the solutions were mixed on a magnetic stirrer.

PROCEDURES FOR TESTS

TABLE 1: COMPOSITION OF VARIOUS FORMULATIONS USED IN THE PREPARED IN SITU GELS.

<i>Formulation</i>	<i>Repaglinide (%)</i>	<i>Carbopol (%)</i>	<i>Sodium citrate (%)</i>	<i>Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose</i>	<i>Calcium chloride (%)</i>	<i>Deionised water (%) up to</i>
<i>CF1</i>	<i>0.1</i>	<i>0.2</i>	<i>0.17</i>	<i>0.5</i>	<i>0.05</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>CF2</i>	<i>0.1</i>	<i>0.4</i>	<i>0.17</i>	<i>0.5</i>	<i>0.05</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>CF3</i>	<i>0.1</i>	<i>0.8</i>	<i>0.17</i>	<i>0.5</i>	<i>0.05</i>	<i>10</i>
<i>CF4</i>	<i>0.1</i>	<i>1.2</i>	<i>0.17</i>	<i>0.5</i>	<i>0.05</i>	<i>10</i>

Physical Appearance and pH

All the prepared batches of polymeric solutions of vanlafaxine HCL were checked for their clarity and the pH. After administration of the prepared solutions in 0.1 mol L⁻¹ HCl, pH 1.2, the time required for gel formation and consistency of gel formed was checked visually. The pH was also measured in each of the solution of sodium alginate based in situ solutions of vanlafaxine HCL, using a calibrated digital pH meter at 25°C.

Viscosity measurement of the in-situ gelling solutions

Viscosity of the sols were determined using a Brookfield digital viscometer (Model no LVDV 2P230) with the spindle number 1. The temperature of the 5 mL samples was kept at 28 ± 1 °C during each measurement which lasted 30 sec, and the experiments were performed in triplicate.

In-vitro buoyancy

The in-vitro buoyancy study was performed using the 100 mL of simulated gastric fluid (pH = 1.2) in a beaker kept under slow stirring using magnetic stirrer. The medium temperature was kept at 37°C. A 10 mL sample of the prepared solution (in-situ gelling formulation) was drawn up with the help of a disposable syringe and injected into the beaker containing the medium without much turbulence. The time for the gel to come to surface (floating lag time) and the time the gel remained floated on the medium surface (floating time) were recorded.

Swelling Index

A gel of 100mg was weighed accurately (W1). It was kept in a petridish and 50ml of 0.1 N HCl was added. The petridish was kept aside for 24 hrs. The weight of swollen matrix gel (W2) was measured and swelling index was calculated using following formulae: Swelling Index = $(W2-W1/W1)*100$ Where, W1 = initial weight of gel (100mg), W2 = weight of swollen matrix after 24 hrs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical Appearance and pH

Physical characterization parameters are reported in table 1. All the formulation had off white to pale yellow colored solution. They had pH in the range of 6.9 -7.5.

Floating Behavior

The buoyancy lag time varied with the formulation variables. Formulation F5 exhibited the least buoyancy lag time (28s) while formulation F1 exhibited the highest lag time (111 s). Irrespective of formulation variables, buoyancy duration was more than 20 hours. All the prepared batches were evaluated for their floating properties in simulated gastric fluid. The time for formulation to come to the medium surface (floating lag time) and the time period for which the formulation maintained floated on the medium surface (duration of floating) were determined.

TABLE 2: IN VITRO FLOATING STUDIES.

0.2% carbopol

0.4% carbopol

0.8% carbopol

1.2% carbopol

Viscosity of In Situ Gelling Solutions

The viscosity of the formulations increased with an increase in carbopol concentration. This phenomenon is a consequence of increasing chain interaction with an increase in polymer concentration. Calcium chloride, which is the source of cations, increased the viscosity of the formulation. This change in viscosity is due to the proportional increase in the amount of dispersed calcium chloride

CONCLUSION

The formulated in situ gel containing repaglinide has passed the in vitro tests. As it is a floating drug delivery system it has increased retention in stomach and thus increased and prolonged release of drug. However in vivo tests were not carried out. Thus, it can be concluded that the prepared formulation can be used after, further in vivo and kinetic studies.

Author's statement:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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